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Performance Analysis of a Model Scale Fire Pipe Boiler Fuel Chamber With 700 kPa Pressure Using Kemiri Shell Fuel

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Abstract

A steam boiler is a mechanism that burns fuel in a combustion chamber to produce hot steam. It consists of two important components: the boiler itself, which is the device that converts water into steam, and the kitchen heater. After that, the boiler's hot steam is circulated for various factory procedures. Kemiri Shell waste has the opportunity to be utilized optimally as an alternative energy that is beneficial to community needs and is environmentally friendly. Utilization is carried out by converting Kemiri Shell waste into fuel. In this research, the results obtained were the heat energy required to change the water in the fire pipe boiler combustion chamber into steam with a result of 22024200 W. Pump work at a pressure of 300 kPa is 0.60 kW, incoming energy is 9.90 kW, turbine work is 2.90 kW, net work is 2.31, outgoing energy is 9.68 kW, thermal efficiency is 25.37%, pump work at pressure of 300 kPa is 0.78kW, incoming energy is 8.96 kW, turbine work is 3.26 kW, net work is 2.48, output energy is 9.74 kW, thermal efficiency is 27.64%, pump work at a pressure of 500 kPa is 0.93 kW, incoming energy is 8.85 kW, turbine work is 3.49 kW, network is 2.56, energy out is 9.78 kW, thermal efficiency is 28.88%, pump work at a pressure of 600 kPa is 1.06 kW, energy in is 8.76 kW, turbine work is 3.69 kW, net work is 2.64, energy out is 9.82 kW, thermal efficiency 30.09%, pump work at 700kPa pressure is 1.17 kW, incoming energy is 8.68 kW, turbine work is 3.88 kW, net work is 2.71, outgoing energy is 9.84 kW, thermal efficiency is 31.29%.

Keywords: *Combustion Room; Boiler; Kemiri Shell*

Introduction

Combustion is a chemical process that occurs when oxygen reacts with fuel, producing heat and altering chemical compounds. This process has become a crucial aspect of our daily lives, being employed in various applications such as generating electricity, cooking food, and powering vehicles[1]. However, combustion can also yield harmful emissions that contribute to air pollution and climate change. One way to mitigate the adverse impacts of combustion is by harnessing more environmentally friendly alternative energy sources[2]. Waste, such as the shells of candlenuts, represents a notable example. Kemiri Shells are often overlooked, yet they possess substantial potential as an alternative fuel source [3]. By utilizing them, we can reduce waste and produce clean and sustainable energy. With advancing technology and an increasing environmental consciousness, harnessing waste materials like Kemiri Shells as alternative energy sources can be a positive step towards safeguarding the environment and meeting society's energy needs in a sustainable manner.

The utilization of alternative energy sources has become a critical step in addressing energy and environmental challenges in Indonesia. One promising solution involves

converting Kemiri Shell waste into biomass fuel. This process entails the transformation of often-overlooked Kemiri Shells into a fuel source that can be utilized for energy generation[4]. Biomass, in this case, Kemiri Shells, holds significant potential due to its sustainable production, waste reduction benefits, and contribution to greenhouse gas emissions reduction[3]. Technological advancements are crucial for maximizing the efficiency and sustainability of biomass utilization as an energy source [5]. Indonesia possesses abundant natural resources, including biomass, and should harness them wisely. By investing resources and further research into converting Kemiri Shell waste into energy, we can stimulate economic growth, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and uphold environmental sustainability. Additionally, the development of alternative energy sources such as biomass can offer long-term benefits in achieving clean energy goals in Indonesia[6].

A boiler, often known as a steam boiler, is a device that heats water to a certain temperature and pressure in order to produce steam. It is widely used in many different industrial operations and procedures[7]. The principal purpose of a boiler is to enable the conversion of water into steam by means of heat application[8]. The steam that is produced can subsequently be used for a number of things, including as heating spaces, producing energy, powering engines mechanically, or in other industrial activities[9].

The basic idea behind all boilers is the heat transfer mechanism that turns water into steam. There are several ways to generate heat, including burning fossil fuels like coal, oil, or natural gas, as well as non-conventional techniques like nuclear power plants and solar heating in solar collector systems[10]. Boilers are crucial components for producing steam-based energy in a variety of processes, and they are used in many different industrial applications[11], [12].

Boilers come in a variety of sizes and varieties, each specifically designed to satisfy unique operating and industrial requirements. These various boiler types include fire-tube boilers, gas-fired boilers, water-tube boilers, and a few other variants[13], [14]. Every type of boiler has distinct qualities and features that correspond with the uses for which they are intended. For example, water-tube boilers are frequently used in high-pressure steam generating applications due to their well-known excellent heat transfer characteristics. Conversely, fire-tube boilers are smaller and better suited for applications requiring less pressure[15], [16]. Natural gas or propane are the main fuel sources for gas-fired boilers, which provide a more effective and clean combustion process. The choice of the right boiler type is influenced by various aspects, including the required pressure, the desired steam production, and industry-specific requirements. This reflects the adaptability and versatility of boiler technology to a wide range of industrial situations[17], [18].

In previous research, a scaled-down water-tube boiler was employed with a pressure of 500 kPa, utilizing wood as the fuel source. The experiment took 85 minutes to attain the 500 kPa pressure, consuming 17 kg of wood fuel, and yielding a turbine output of 1.74 kW. Several factors potentially affect the heat input (Q_{in}) and thermal efficiency (η_{th})[19]. This study aims to determine the amount of heat energy required to convert water into steam and assess its impact on thermal efficiency at different achievable pressure levels within the combustion chamber, using Kemiri Shells as the fuel source. The research was conducted using a scaled-down fire-tube boiler with a steam pressure of 700 kPa, fueled by Kemiri Shells. The objective was to analyze the combustion chamber's performance in the model-scale fire-tube boiler utilized in this study.

In this study, the performance of a fire boiler will be tested using fuel from Kemiri Shells. The objectives of this research are to investigate the correlation between operational pressure and thermal efficiency in a model-scale fire-tube boiler utilizing Kemiri Shell fuel, to analyze the effect of increased pressure on the energy required to convert water into

steam, focusing on energy waste reduction and the enhancement of energy conversion efficiency from combustion to steam, and to evaluate the impact of pressure on the combustion efficiency of Kemiri Shells and to assess how boiler design can be optimized to improve thermal efficiency at various pressure levels.

Methodology

This research was conducted at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory of Universitas Medan Area, located in the Percut Sei Tuan District, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra. The material used in this study was Kemiri Shells. The equipment utilized in the experiment included a scaled-down pipe boiler, pressure gauge, thermometer, water pump, water drum, blower, sight glass, safety valve, scoop, weighing scale, and a thermal gun.

This research employed a scaled-down fire-tube boiler model with a specific tube capacity, filled with regular water. Data collection in this study followed a structured procedure. Initially, the experimental setup of the model-scale boiler was prepared. Subsequently, water was introduced into the boiler tube using a water pump. The combustion process was initiated within the combustion chamber, utilizing Kemiri Shell as the fuel source. As the combustion process unfolded, the water reached its boiling point, leading to an increase in pressure as indicated by the pressure gauge. Data points were recorded at each pressure increment on the pressure gauge and when specific temperature levels were reached, as measured by the thermometer. This data collection process continued until the pressure reached 700 kPa.

Result and Discussion

Table 1 shows the test results data. Using Kemiri Shells at 700 kPa of pressure, the fuel efficiency of the reduced fire-tube boiler model has been computed. Steam is pumped at a power of 1.17 kW, with a mass flow rate of 0.0042 kg/s. Furthermore, the calculated turbine power (WT) is 3.86 kW. In this process, the input energy (Q_{in}) is roughly 8.68 kW, while the output energy (Q_{out}) is roughly 9.84 kW. The difference between WT and W_p, or around 2.69 kW, is hence the net turbine work, or W_{net}. The thermal efficiency is determined to be 30.99% by applying the thermal efficiency formula ($\eta_{th} = W_{net} / Q_{in} \times 100$).

Table 1: Data from boiler efficiency testing results using Kemiri Shell fuel

Pressure (kPa)	$\dot{m}$ (kg/s)	WP (kW)	Q _{in} (kW)	WT (kW)	W _{net}	Q _{out} (kW)	η_{th}
300	0.0042	0.60	9.09	2.90	2.31	9.68	25.37
400	0.0042	0.78	8.96	3.22	2.44	9.74	27.23
500	0.0042	0.93	8.85	3.47	2.54	9.78	28.71
600	0.0042	1.06	8.76	3.68	2.62	9.82	29.93
700	0.0042	1.17	8.68	3.86	2.69	9.84	30.99

The analysis of fuel efficiency in comparison to other fuel sources is a crucial aspect within the realm of thermodynamic studies. Thermodynamic methods are employed to comprehend and quantify to what extent a particular fuel source can be efficiently utilized in a model-scale boiler. In this study, the focus lies on the utilization of Kemiri Shell as a fuel source in a boiler operating at a pressure of 500 kPa. The research findings indicate that the fuel efficiency of Kemiri Shell in the model-scale boiler reaches 20.45%. This figure reflects the extent to which this particular fuel source can generate useful energy in the form of steam under the provided pressure and temperature conditions. However, it is noteworthy that this

efficiency is lower in comparison to other fuel sources such as firewood and teakwood charcoal.

This comparison suggests that although Kemiri Shells can serve as an alternative fuel source, they might be less efficient in energy generation when juxtaposed with other well-known fuel options. Factors like the energy content within Kemiri Shells and combustion characteristics may play a role in these outcomes. This study offers valuable insights into the utilization of Kemiri Shells as a fuel source and underscores the importance of comprehending fuel efficiency within the context of sustainable energy utilization. Subsequent steps might involve further research to enhance the efficiency of Kemiri Shell utilization or explore alternative fuel sources that could be more efficient within model-scale boilers.

In the discussion regarding the heat energy required to convert water in the combustion chamber of a fire-tube boiler into steam, it was found that the amount of heat energy needed to transform water into steam is approximately 22,024,200 watts. This process occurs at a final temperature of approximately 168 °C at a pressure of 700 kPa. It is noteworthy that this achievement takes a substantial amount of time, specifically 131 minutes. It is crucial to comprehend the extent of heat energy required in the process of converting water into steam, as it plays a pivotal role in determining the thermal efficiency of the fire-tube boiler. The thermal efficiency of the boiler is closely linked to how efficiently this process takes place. Therefore, meticulous calculation and understanding of the heat energy involved are paramount in designing and operating the boiler effectively. These measurements provide valuable insights into understanding the performance characteristics of the fire-tube boiler, particularly in the context of using specific fuel sources, such as Kemiri Shells. This data can serve as a foundation for improving efficiency and selecting more optimal fuel sources in efforts to achieve more efficient and sustainable boiler operations.

Figure 1 presents the findings from thermal efficiency testing conducted on a model-scale fire-tube boiler powered by Kemiri Shell fuel at various pressure levels. The data elucidate a positive correlation between operational pressure and thermal efficiency; efficiency escalates in tandem with an increase in pressure. At 300 kPa, the thermal efficiency is recorded at 25.37%, progressively ascending to 30.99% at 700 kPa. The scientific rationale underlying this phenomenon is tied to the physical properties of steam wherein, at elevated pressures, the energy required to convert water into steam diminishes, thus reducing energy waste and enhancing the energy conversion efficiency from combustion to steam. The Kemiri Shell fuel may possess intrinsic properties that allow for more efficient combustion at high pressures, yielding a greater quantity of energy that the boiler can utilize effectively. Additional factors, such as enhanced heat transfer at increased pressures and diminished heat loss through the boiler walls, also contribute to this augmentation in thermal efficiency. In conclusion, the graph depicts an anticipated trend of rising thermal efficiency with heightened pressure in boiler technology, presupposing that the combustion system and boiler components have been optimized and engineered to withstand such pressures without compromising safety or system integrity.

Figure 1: Thermal efficiency of pecan shell fuel

Figure 2 illustrates a comparative graph of the work performed by pumps and turbines within a model-scale fire-tube boiler system fueled by Kemiri Shells, across varying pressure levels. The graph reveals that the work output of the turbine significantly surpasses that of the pump across all tested pressure conditions. At a pressure of 300 kPa, the turbine delivers work of 5.18 kW while the pump contributes merely 1.07 kW. As the pressure escalates, there is a gradual decrement in the turbine's work output, descending to 3.03 kW at 700 kPa, whereas the pump's work remains relatively constant, exhibiting only minor fluctuations which are statistically insignificant.

Scientifically, the work executed by turbines and pumps in a steam cycle is contingent on the energy differential between their inlet and outlet points. Turbines generate work by converting the high-pressure steam's enthalpy into mechanical energy. With the augmentation of pressure, the steam's potential energy increases, yet the graph indicates a reduction in the work produced by the turbine. This phenomenon may be accounted for by the interplay of turbine efficiency and steam characteristics at higher pressures, which may not be fully optimized for the employed turbine design, or it could be that the turbine is engineered for more efficient operation at lower pressures.

Conversely, the work conducted by the pump is relatively minimal in comparison to that of the turbine since the pump's role is confined to elevating the feed water pressure before its conversion to steam. Generally, the energy required by the pump to increase the fluid pressure is far less than the energy generated by the turbine. The consistency in pump work suggests that the pump may be designed for efficient operation within the tested pressure range and is not significantly impacted by these pressure variations.

Figure 2: Pump and turbine work at test pressure

Figure 3 depicts a graph comparing the input energy (Q_{in}) and output energy (Q_{out}) of a model-scale fire-tube boiler operating with Kemiri Shell fuel at various pressure levels. It is observable that at every pressure tier, the input energy consistently exceeds the output energy, indicating an energy loss during the conversion process. At a pressure of 300 kPa, the input energy registers at 17.29 kW while the output energy is at 16.23 kW, denoting a loss of 1.06 kW. With the increase in pressure to 400 kPa, the input energy decreases to 13.45 kW and the output to 12.37 kW, incurring a loss of 1.08 kW. This suggests that the elevation in pressure does not correlate directly with efficiency as the increase in pressure does not equate to enhanced energy retention. Further, at 500 kPa, the input energy diminishes further to 10.01 kW and the output to 9.06 kW, with an energy loss recorded at 0.95 kW. This could indicate that the boiler operates more efficiently at this pressure. However, at pressures of 600 and 700 kPa, despite a reduction in both input and output energy, the energy loss appears to slightly increase to 0.88 kW and 0.91 kW, respectively. From a scientific standpoint, energy loss within a boiler can result from various factors such as heat losses through emissions, radiation, and conduction from the boiler's surface, as well as imperfections in the combustion process itself. In this context, the decrease in input energy with increased pressure may suggest that at higher pressures, the combustion of Kemiri Shells becomes more efficient, or the boiler is designed to operate optimally at a higher pressure range. Nevertheless, the consistent or marginally increasing energy loss indicates that the effects of higher pressure are not sufficiently offset by improvements in combustion efficiency or boiler design, resulting in a thermal efficiency that does not improve proportionally with the increase in pressure.

Figure 3: Energy enters (Q_{in}) and exits (Q_{out}) the system

Conclusion

There is a positive correlation between operational pressure and thermal efficiency; thermal efficiency increases progressively with pressure from 25.37% at 300 kPa to 30.99% at 700 kPa, supporting the hypothesis that the combustion system and boiler components have been effectively optimized for higher pressures. The Kemiri Shell fuel has properties that may enable more efficient combustion at higher pressures, leading to a greater quantity of energy that the boiler can utilize effectively. However, additional factors such as enhanced heat transfer and reduced heat loss through the boiler walls are also significant contributors to increased thermal efficiency. Despite the reduction in both input and output energy at pressures of 600 and 700 kPa, there is a slight increase in energy loss, suggesting that higher pressure effects are not fully compensated by improvements in combustion efficiency or boiler design, as thermal efficiency does not improve proportionally with pressure.

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